

LEVEL OF THE COORDINATION OF SDRRM COORDINATORS AND LEVEL OF CAPABILITIES IN DISASTER RESPONSE OF HIGH-RISK SCHOOLS IN FOURTH CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of coordination of the SDRRM Coordinators and the level of capabilities in disaster response of the high-risk schools in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon for the School Year 2023 – 2024. The research utilized a descriptive–correlational design with a quantitative approach to assess coordination and capability levels and explore their relationship. Data were collected through a researcher-made survey questionnaire, which underwent expert validation and reliability testing using the Sielge Reliability Calculator to ensure internal consistency. Respondents were purposively selected, including school heads, teachers, and SDRRM coordinators directly involved in disaster risk reduction management. Statistical tools such as weighted mean and standard deviation were used to analyze levels of coordination and capabilities. At the same time, Spearman's Rho was employed to determine the correlation between the two variables. Results indicated that SDRRM coordination in high–risk schools were generally moderate, with strengths in preparedness, response, and recovery, but areas such as prevention and mitigation showed room for improvement. Regarding disaster response capabilities, schools were moderately capable in human resources, facilities, and innovation, while policy planning and procedural frameworks were identified as areas of firm performance. Furthermore, the study found a significant positive relationship between the level of coordination of SDRRM coordinators and the disaster response capabilities of high–risk schools. It implies that better coordination directly contributes to

enhanced school readiness and capacity to manage disaster risks. Based on the findings, an intervention plan was developed to strengthen coordination mechanisms and improve overall disaster management capacity.

Keywords: *Capabilities, Coordination, High Risk Schools, SDRRM, Descriptive – Correlational design*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines' location in the Pacific Ring of Fire and typhoon zone and its topography and geology make it vulnerable to natural and artificial disasters. Disasters and dangers that the nation must deal with include landslides, earthquakes, cyclones, volcanic eruptions, and flooding. Furthermore, according to the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR), it was placed third (3rd) out of 173 nations in the 2012 World Risk Index for disaster risk (Gaillard et. al, 2012).

The Philippine government has created designs to offset the consequences of both natural and artificial calamities. Increasing the nation's and vulnerable communities' resilience to natural disasters and minimizing property loss and damage are the primary goals of the laws and regulations that have been developed. Furthermore, R.A. New plans and regulations regarding implementing various measures and activities in all Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) phases were made possible by Act 10121, also known as the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act. It led to a paradigm change from reactive to proactive, from centralized, top-down administration to a participative, bottom-up approach to disaster risk reduction (RA 10121, 2010).

The National DRRM Framework (NDRRMF) and National DRRM Plan (NDRRMP) were created due to this Act. A nation with "safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient Filipino communities toward sustainable development" is what the NDRRMF and NDRRMP envision. The four subject areas a) Prevention and Mitigation, b) Preparedness, c) Response, and d) Rehabilitation and Recovery—were developed in tandem with the paradigm change. Long-term objectives and initiatives at each location will help DRRM achieve its overarching mission. The NDRRMF states that to achieve its goals and objectives more successfully, resources allocated to the four thematic areas must prioritize disaster preparedness, catastrophe prevention and mitigation, and climate change adaptation (NDRRMF, 2011). Although the DRRM statute legally supports its disaster risk reduction guidelines, the Department of Education (DepEd) published DepEd No. 37, s. 2017 as the foundation for a more thorough Disaster Risk Reduction Management in the Basic Education Framework. This framework calls for institutionalized DRRM structures, systems, procedures, and practices in DepEd offices and schools. Furthermore, powerful typhoons and severe flooding that destroy school property are two ways calamities always find their way into schools. Because of this, the Philippines' disaster-proneness calls for a closer examination of its current disaster-related policies (Catanus, 2018).

Schools are supposed to serve as examples of disaster avoidance since they are universal venues for exchanging knowledge and skills. One of the best indicators of how sound education has been delivered over the years is the ability to mitigate disasters successfully. In order to ensure the safety of students and their families in an emergency, the school system implemented a DRRMP. Natural disasters can disrupt and ruin students' formal or informal learning processes. Whether they are artificial, biohazardous, or natural, these calamities have had a particularly negative impact on school communities, with kids, staff, and teachers among those dead, maimed, or displaced. Classes are further disrupted by the fact that schools are frequently used as evacuation shelters. Initiatives for disaster risk management must be integrated and promoted immediately to lower the risks associated with disasters and lessen their effects. Creating action plans for Infant and Young Child Feeding in Emergencies (IFE) is one way to improve school resilience, especially in high-risk populations. The Philippines is dedicated to integrating Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) into the curriculum.

In 2007, the Secretary of the Department of Education (DepEd) sent an order memo to all department offices, with a focus on public and private schools, directing them to prioritize disaster risk reduction management's mainstreaming in the school system and to make sure that DRR-related projects and programs were coordinated. Thus, this solid foundation and dedication served as the basis for the MDRD Education initiative.

The researcher believes that people could encounter unexpected disasters at any time of day, so they tried to ascertain the degree of coordination of the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program (SDRRMP) and the level of capabilities to respond to the High-Risk Schools. The researcher is motivated to investigate the degree of DRR coordination for school safety in the relevant municipalities because of the current circumstances.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of coordination of the SDRRM Coordinators and the level of capabilities in disaster response of the high-risk schools in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon as the basis for the formulation of the Intervention Plan.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the level of coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the high-risk schools as to the following thematic areas:
 - 1.1 Disaster Prevention and Mitigation;
 - 1.2 Disaster Preparedness;
 - 1.3 Disaster Response;
 - 1.4 Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation?

2. What is the level of the capabilities of the high-risk schools in disaster response with regards to:

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- 2.1. Human Resources;
 - 2.2 Material Facilities;
 - 2.3 Knowledge, innovation, and education;
 - 2.4 Policies, plans and procedures;
 - 2.5 Capacities and mechanism?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of coordination of the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management coordinators and the level of capabilities in disaster response of the risk schools?

4. What intervention plan can be developed by the researcher based from the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive–correlational quantitative research design to examine the level of coordination of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Coordinators and the capabilities of high–risk schools in disaster response within the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon for the School Year 2023 – 2024. This research was conducted in five high–risk public elementary schools located in the Municipalities of Alabat, Atimonan, Calauag, Plaridel, and Quezon areas that belong to the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon, situated in the CALABARZON region of the Philippines. This District was identified as high–risk based on geographic vulnerability and official data from the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (MDRRMO) and Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator (MPDC). The selected schools were CB Encarnado Integrated School in Alabat, Tagbakin Elementary School in Atimonan, Sumilang Elementary School in Calauag, Ilosong Elementary School in Plaridel, and Gumubat Elementary School in Quezon. Due to their coastal and mountainous terrain, these areas are highly exposed to natural hazards such as typhoons, floods, landslides, and storm surges.

Purposive sampling was employed in selecting respondents, which included school heads, SDRRM coordinators, and teachers from the identified high–risk schools. This sampling method was chosen to ensure the participation of individuals with direct responsibilities and relevant experience in disaster management. Fifty-one respondents were involved: 5 school heads, 5 SDRRM Coordinators, and 41 teachers.

The main instrument for the data collection was a researcher-made survey questionnaire adapted from Comighud (2020), which focused on key DRRM aspects such as disaster prevention and mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part I assessed the level of DRRM program coordination, while Part II assessed disaster response capabilities, including human resources, materials and facilities, education and training, and institutional mechanisms. The instrument underwent

content validation by three to five experts, including MDRRM officials, school administrators, and district DRRM coordinators. Its reliability was tested using the Sielge Reliability Calculator to ensure internal consistency. Pilot testing was conducted with a non-sample group to validate the clarity and relevance of the items.

Before data gathering, the researcher obtained permission from school authorities and the original author of the instrument. Formal request letters were sent to the Public Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisors, and school principals. Once approved, the survey was administered via Google Forms for respondents with internet access, while printed copies were distributed to schools in areas with unstable connectivity. After collection, the researcher thoroughly reviewed the completed questionnaires to ensure completeness and accuracy. The data were then tallied, organized, and subjected to statistical analysis.

For data analysis, weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of coordination among DRRM Coordinators and the capabilities of high-risk schools in disaster response. Both constructs were assessed using a five-point Likert scale, with descriptors ranging from "Very Well Coordinated" to "Not Coordinated" for coordination and from "Very Much Capable" to "Not Capable" for capabilities. Spearman's Rho correlation coefficient was employed to examine the relationship between coordination levels and disaster response capabilities. This nonparametric test was appropriate due to the ordinal nature of the Likert-scale data and the potential non-normal distribution of responses. The correlation strength was interpreted using the standard Spearman's scale, ranging from "very weak" to "robust" correlation.

The scope of this study was limited to the five identified high-risk public elementary schools in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. It focused solely on examining the internal coordination practices of DRRM Coordinators and evaluating the schools' capacity for disaster preparedness and response. The study's limitations include reliance on self-reported data, which may be subject to bias, and the inability to generalize findings beyond similar geographic or demographic settings. External factors such as political climate, budget constraints, and community involvement were not within the study's purview but may influence DRRM implementation.

RESULTS

The result of the study is reported based on the objectives stated earlier as follows:

1. Level of coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the high-risk schools Disaster Prevention and Mitigation. The coordination levels of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) Coordinators in high-risk schools across five municipalities, with a composite mean of 3.36, categorized as "Moderately Coordinated (MC)." This indicates that while some efforts are made, improvements are still necessary. Table 1 shows that the highest mean

3.67 for District 1 Quezon is for "Increased disaster resiliency of infrastructure system," while the lowest mean 2.67 is for "Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Reduction Management DRRM mainstreamed and integrated into national, sectoral, regional, and local development policies, plans, and budget." In District 2 Alabat, the highest mean of 3.90 is for "Community-based and scientific DRR-CCA assessment, mapping, analysis, and monitoring," and the lowest mean of 2.80 appears in "DRRM and CCA mainstreamed and integrated into policies." District 3 Calauag shows the highest mean of 4.00 in "Community-based and scientific DRR-CCA assessment, mapping, analysis, and monitoring," but the lowest mean of 3.40 is also in "DRRM and CCA mainstreamed and integrated into policies." In District 4 Atimonan, the highest mean of 3.73 is for "Community-based and scientific DRR-CAA Assessment, mapping, analysis, and monitoring," while the lowest mean of 2.73 is found in "DRRM and CCA mainstreamed and integrated into policies." Last but not least, District 5 Plaridel has the lowest mean of 2.45 for "DRRM and CCA mainstreamed and integrated into policies," and the highest mean of 3.91 for "Maintain close coordination with the local DRRM Council on the conduct of preparedness activities and response needs among others. In terms of disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM), the towns of Alabat, Atimonan, Calauag, Plaridel, and Quezon in the 4th District of Quezon Province have advanced. The data show that their coordination attempts, however, fall short of the high levels of coordination that are expected and are only moderately effective, with their highlighted weakness at climate change adaptability and mainstreaming into policies.

Table 1. Level of Coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the High-Risk schools in terms of Disaster Prevention and Mitigation

Indicators	Mean					Total			
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD	VI	
I. Disaster Prevention and Mitigation									
1. Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) are mainstreamed and integrated into national, sectoral, regional, and local development policies, plans, and budgets.	2.67	2.80	3.40	2.73	2.45	2.80	0.872	MC	
2. Increased disaster resiliency of	3.67	3.40	3.70	2.91	3.18	3.35	0.844	WC	

infrastructure systems									
3. Community-based and scientific DRR-CCA assessment, mapping, analysis, and monitoring	2.78	3.90	4.00	3.73	2.82	3.45	1.026	WC	
4. Communities have access to effective and applicable disaster risk financing and insurance companies.	3.22	3.50	3.80	3.18	3.00	3.33	0.887	MC	
5. End-to-end monitoring, forecasting, and early warning systems are established and/or improved.	2.56	3.00	3.70	2.91	3.55	3.16	1.120	MC	
6. Ensure the establishment of an Early Warning System	2.78	3.60	3.90	2.82	3.45	3.31	0.905	MC	
7. Conduct an annual student-led risk identification and mapping within and around the school premises to ensure a safe environment that is conducive to teaching and learning.	3.00	3.70	3.70	3.36	3.45	3.45	0.986	WC	
8. Maintain close coordination with the local DRRM Council on the conduct of preparedness activities and response needs, among others.	3.22	3.50	3.80	3.18	3.91	3.53	1.155	WC	
9. Provide capacity-building activities for teachers, non-teaching staff, and learners on DRRM.	2.89	3.20	3.60	3.18	3.55	3.29	0.944	MC	

10. Maintain, disseminate, and post relevant and updated emergency hotlines in strategic locations throughout the school.	3.11	3.90	4.00	3.64	3.73	3.69	1.068	WC
11. Post-safety and preparedness measures and evacuation plans	3.44	3.80	3.60	3.45	3.64	3.59	1.134	WC
Composite Mean						3.36	0.995	MC

Legend:

4.20-5.00 – Very Well Coordinated (VWC)	D1 – D5	District 1 - 5
3.40-4.20 – Well Coordinated (WC)		
2.60-3.40 – Moderately Coordinated (MC)		
1.80-2.60 – Less Coordinated (LC)		
1.00-1.79 – Not Coordinated (NC)		

2. Level of Coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the High-Risk Schools in terms of Disaster Preparedness. The composite mean of 3.59, categorized as "Well Coordinated (WC)," shows that there is strong coordination in disaster preparedness across all municipalities, although some areas still require improvement. District 1 (Quezon) has the highest mean of 4.00 for "Organize school DRRM team to support the implementation of preparedness and response measures," and the lowest mean of 2.33 for "Conduct disaster preparedness measures, including but not limited to quarterly multi-hazard drills." The highest mean of 4.20 is found in District 2 Alabat for "Increased disaster resiliency of infrastructure systems" and "Maintain the safekeeping of vital school records and learning materials," while the lowest mean of 3.20 is found in "Conduct disaster preparedness measures, including but not limited to quarterly multi-hazard drills applicable to the school's identified hazards such as earthquakes, fire, and flood." The highest mean of 4.20 is found in District 3 Calauag for "Maintain safekeeping of vital school records and learning materials," while the lowest mean of 3.60 is found in "Strengthened partnership and coordination among all key players and stakeholders." The highest mean of 4.00 in District 4 Atimonan is found in "Maintain the safekeeping of vital school records. With the lowest 3.09 "Conduct disaster preparedness measures, including but not limited to quarterly multi-hazard drills applicable to the school's identified hazards such as earthquakes, fire, and flood." Last but not least, District 5 Plaridel displays its highest mean of 3.82 for "Pre-identify possible Temporary Learning Spaces (TLS) and Integrate DRRM in regular school programs," with the lowest mean of 3.36 for "Conduct disaster preparedness measures, including but not limited to quarterly multi-hazard drills applicable to the school's identified hazards such as earthquakes, fire, and flood and Maintain safekeeping of vital school records and learning materials." The results of the study indicate that while disaster preparedness efforts in high-risk schools such as organizing DRRM teams, maintaining the safekeeping of vital school records, and

conducting drills are generally well-coordinated, there remain notable areas requiring improvement, the study also reveals that although the municipalities of Quezon, Alabat, Calauag, Atimonan, and Plaridel have generally coordinated their disaster preparedness efforts in high-risk schools such as setting up DRRM teams, keeping important school records safe, and holding drills there are still some areas that need improvement.

Table 2. Level of Coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the High-Risk Schools in terms of Disaster Preparedness

Indicators	Mean					Total		VI
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD	
B. Disaster Preparedness								
1. Increased level of awareness and enhanced capacity of the community to the threats and impacts of all hazards	3.56	4.10	3.90	3.73	3.64	3.78	1.154	WC
2. Communities are equipped with the necessary skills and capability to cope with the impact of disasters.	3.22	3.50	3.80	3.18	3.73	3.49	1.190	WC
3. Increased disaster resiliency of infrastructure systems	3.22	4.20	3.90	3.91	3.64	3.78	1.006	WC
4. Developed and coordinated comprehensive national and local preparedness policies, plans, and systems	2.56	3.30	3.80	3.36	3.55	3.33	1.108	MC
5. Strengthened partnership and coordination among all key players and stakeholders	2.56	3.70	3.60	3.55	3.55	3.41	1.080	WC
6. Conduct disaster preparedness measures, including but not limited to quarterly multi-hazard drills applicable to the school's identified hazards such as earthquakes, fire, and flood.	2.33	3.20	4.10	3.09	3.36	3.24	1.142	MC
7. Maintain the safekeeping of vital school records and learning materials.	3.44	4.20	4.20	4.00	3.36	3.84	1.120	WC
8. Organize the school DRRM team to support the implementation of preparedness and response measures.	4.00	3.90	4.00	3.55	3.55	3.78	1.119	WC
9. Ensure the availability of updated baseline data of the school.	3.44	3.70	4.00	3.82	3.64	3.73	1.250	WC

Table 3. Level of Coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the High-Risk Schools in terms of Disaster Response

Indicators	Mean					Total		VI
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD	
C. Disaster Response								
1. Well-established disaster response and relief operations	3.78	3.80	4.20	3.64	3.36	3.75	0.956	WC
2. Adequate and prompt assessment of needs and damages	3.89	3.80	4.20	3.73	3.64	3.84	1.046	WC
3. Integrated and coordinated Search, Rescue, and Retrieval (SRR) capacity	3.33	3.80	4.00	3.36	3.82	3.67	1.125	WC
4. Temporary shelter and/or structural needs are adequately addressed	3.78	3.80	3.80	3.36	3.55	3.65	1.110	WC
5. Basic social services provided to affected population (whether inside or outside ECs)	3.11	3.90	3.90	3.36	3.45	3.55	1.064	WC
6. Psychosocial needs of the affected population addressed	2.89	3.40	4.00	3.09	3.45	3.37	1.131	MC
7. Coordinated and integrated system for early recovery	2.67	3.70	4.20	3.55	3.82	3.61	1.185	WC
8. Monitor the effects of hazards, including the use of the school as an evacuation center	2.56	4.00	4.00	3.09	3.45	3.43	1.100	WC
9. Track all school personnel during disaster and /or emergencies	3.22	3.60	4.00	3.45	3.45	3.55	0.966	WC
10. Prepare and submit reports on the effects of any hazards	3.78	4.50	4.20	3.55	3.73	3.94	1.047	WC
11. Ensure implementation of DepEd Order No. 43 s. 2012 or the "Guidelines on the implementation of Executive Order No.66 s. 2012(Prescribing Rules on the cancellation or suspension of classes	3.44	3.70	4.10	3.64	4.00	3.78	1.222	WC

and Work in Government Offices Due to Typhoons, Flooding, other weather disturbances, and Calamities)”									
12. Conduct a rapid assessment of damages after every hazard and submit an assessment of Damage Report (RADar) within 72 hours via SMS	3.44	4.50	3.90	3.82	3.64	3.86	1.020	WC	
13. Facilitate immediate resumption of classes for learning continuity	3.67	4.40	4.10	4.00	3.73	3.98	0.969	WC	
Composite Mean						3.69	1.072	WC	

Legend:

- 4.20-5.00 – Very Well Coordinated (VWC) D1 – D5 District 1 - 5
- 3.40-4.20 – Well Coordinated (WC)
- 2.60-3.40 – Moderately Coordinated (MC)
- 1.80-2.60 – Less Coordinated (LC)
- 1.00-1.79 – Not Coordinated (NC)

4. Level of Coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the High-Risk schools in terms of Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation. The composite mean of 3.70, categorized as "Well Coordinated (WC)," indicates that disaster recovery efforts are generally well-coordinated across the municipalities, although a few areas require improvement. For District 1 (Quezon), the highest mean of 3.90 is for "Damages, losses, and needs to be assessed," while the lowest mean of 3.0 is for "Monitored recovery and rehabilitation intervention being coordinated in the District DRRM." In District 2 Alabat, the highest mean of 4.10 is for "Economic activities restored and, if possible, strengthened or expanded," and "A psychologically sound, safe, and secured citizenry" with a mean of 4.10 as well. The lowest mean of 3.10 is found in "Monitored recovery and rehabilitation intervention being coordinated in the District DRRM." District 3 Calauag has the highest mean of 4.30 for Damages, Losses, and Needs Assessed". The lowest mean of 3.80 is in "Monitored recovery and rehabilitation intervention being coordinated in the District DRRM." In District 4 Atimonan, the highest mean of 3.91 is for " A psychologically sound, safe, and secure citizenry that is protected from the effects of disasters is able to restore to normal functioning after each disaster," with the lowest mean of 3.36 for "Monitored recovery and rehabilitation intervention being coordinated in the District DRRM." Finally, District 5 Plaridel has the highest mean of 3.82 for " A psychologically sound, safe, and secure citizenry that is protected from the effects of disasters is able to restore to normal functioning after each disaster," with the lowest mean of 3.36 for " Damages, Losses, and Needs Assessed."

The data shows that schools across the studied municipalities have made commendable progress in implementing recovery procedures, particularly in assessing damages, supporting psychological recovery, and facilitating infrastructure restoration. Notably, Alabat stands out for its effective post-disaster recovery of economic activities and the promotion of a psychologically resilient community.

Table 4. Level of Coordination of Schools Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators of the High-Risk schools in terms of Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation

Indicators	Mean					Total		
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD	VI
D. Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation								
1. Damages, Losses, and Needs Assessed	3.9	3.80	4.30	3.55	3.36	3.76	1.142	WC
2. Economic activities are restored and if possible, strengthened or expanded	3.8	4.10	4.20	3.82	3.55	3.88	0.931	WC
3. DRRM and CCA elements are mainstreamed in human settlement	3.7	3.50	3.90	3.45	3.64	3.63	1.131	WC
4. Disaster and climate change resilient infrastructure constructed/reconstructed	3.7	3.60	4.20	3.36	3.55	3.67	1.052	WC
5. A psychologically sound, safe, and secure citizenry that is protected from the effects of disasters is able to restore to normal functioning after each disaster	3.6	4.10	3.90	3.91	3.82	3.86	1.096	WC
6. Monitored recovery and rehabilitation intervention being coordinated in the District Disaster Risk Reduction Management	3.0	3.10	3.80	3.36	3.55	3.37	0.999	MC
Composite Mean						3.70	1.058	WC

Legend:

- 4.20-5.00 – Very Well Coordinated (VWC)
- 3.40-4.20 – Well Coordinated (WC)
- 2.60-3.40 – Moderately Coordinated (MC)
- 1.80-2.60 – Less Coordinated (LC)
- 1.00-1.79 – Not Coordinated (NC)

D1 – D5 District 1 - 5

5. Level of the Capabilities of the High-Risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Human Resources. The composite mean of 3.37, interpreted as "Moderately Capable (MC)," For District 1 Quezon, the highest mean of 3.56 is observed in both "Dedicated and adequate resources are available to implement DRRM plans " and " Community participation and decentralization are assured through the delegation of authority and resources to local levels,". The lowest mean of 3.44 is seen in "National policy and legal framework for DRRM exists with decentralized responsibilities and capacities at all levels" and "A platform for DRRM is functioning.". In District 2 Alabat, the highest score of 3.60 is for "National policy and legal framework for DRRM exists with decentralized responsibilities and capacities at all levels". However, the lowest score of 3.10 in "A platform for DRRM is functioning". For District 3 Calauag, which generally scored the highest across all municipalities, the top rating is 3.90 for " Community participation and decentralization are assured through the delegation of authority and resources to local levels,". The lowest, yet still strong, mean of 3.70 appears in both " for "National policy and legal framework for DRRM exists with decentralized responsibilities and capacities at all levels" and Dedicated and adequate resources are available to implement DRRM plans and activities at all administrative levels ". District 4 Atimonan recorded its highest mean of 3.73 in " National policy and legal framework for DRRM exists with decentralized responsibilities and capacities at all levels". The lowest mean of 3.00 in " Dedicated and adequate resources are available to implement DRRM plans and activities at all administrative levels. Finally, District 5 Plaridel scored the highest at 3.00 in " National policy and legal framework for DRRM exists with decentralized responsibilities and capacities at all levels " while all other indicators including " Dedicated and adequate resources are available to implement DRRM plans and activities at all administrative levels", Community participation and decentralization are assured through the delegation of authority and resources to local levels and "A platform for DRRM is functioning" were tied at the lowest mean of 2.91. It suggests that while essential DRRM structures exist across the five municipalities, the quality and comprehensiveness of their human resource strategies differ significantly particularly in areas of leadership, policy execution, and grassroots engagement. Among them, Calauag emerges as the most competent, especially in decentralizing DRRM functions and promoting community involvement.

Table 5. Level of the Capabilities of the High-Risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Human Resources.

Indicators	Mean					Total		VI	
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD		
A. Human Resources									
1. National policy and legal framework for DRRM exists with decentralized responsibilities and capacities at all levels.	3.44	3.60	3.70	3.73	3.00	3.49	1.065	VC	
2. Dedicated and adequate resources are available to implement DRRM plans and	3.56	3.50	3.70	3.00	2.91	3.31	0.927	MC	

activities at all administrative levels.									
3. Community participation and decentralization are assured through the delegation of authority and resources to local levels.	3.56	3.30	3.90	3.55	2.91	3.43	0.944	VC	
4. A platform for DRRM is functioning.	3.44	3.10	3.80	3.00	2.91	3.24	0.907	MC	
Composite Mean						3.37	0.961	MC	

Legend:

- 4.20-5.00 – *Very Well Capable (VMC)* D1 – D5 District 1 - 5
- 3.40-4.20 – *Very Capable (VC)*
- 2.60-3.40 – *Moderately Capable (MC)*
- 1.80-2.60 – *Less Capable (LC)*
- 1.00-1.79 – *Not Capable (NC)*

6. Level of the Capabilities of the High-risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Material Facilities. For District 1 Quezon, the highest mean of 3.78 is in "Systems are in place to monitor, archive, and disseminate data on key hazards and vulnerabilities,". The lowest score of 3.11 is seen in "Early warning systems are in place for all major hazards with outreach to communities". In District 2 Alabat, the highest score of 4.30 is in the same indicator "Systems are in place to monitor, archive, and disseminate data on key hazards and vulnerabilities. However, the lowest mean of 3.20 for " Early warning systems are in place for all major hazards with outreach to communities. District 3 Calauag again shows strong overall performance, with the highest mean of 4.00 in "S Systems are in place to monitor, archive, and disseminate data on key hazards and vulnerabilities," The lowest mean of 3.40 is in " Early warning systems are in place for all major hazards with outreach to communities. For District 4 Atimonan, the highest score of 3.55 is for " National and local risk assessments take account of regional/transboundary risks, with a view to regional cooperation and risk reduction. Its lowest score of 3.09 in " National and local risk assessments based on hazard data and vulnerability information are available and include risk assessments for key sectors. Lastly, District 5 Plaridel recorded its highest score of 2.91 in " Systems are in place to monitor, archive, and disseminate data on key hazards and vulnerabilities" while the lowest mean of 2.64 is for " National and local risk assessments based on hazard data and vulnerability information are available and include risk assessments for key sectors". The moderate capability of high-risk schools in terms of Material Facilities for Disaster Response, with a composite mean of 3.39, suggests that several municipalities require improvement. Disparities in implementation are noticeable, especially in early warning systems and localized risk assessments, despite the fact that all five municipalities show efforts to set up risk monitoring systems and risk assessments.

response infrastructure, like risk assessments and data monitoring systems, there are still gaps in terms of full implementation, especially in areas like sectoral risk analysis and early warning systems. Furthermore, when it came to performing thorough risk assessments based on hazard and vulnerability data, a number of municipalities especially Plaridel and Atimonan scored poorly, particularly in crucial areas like infrastructure, health, and education.

Table 7. Level of the Capabilities of the High-Risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Knowledge, Innovation and Education

Indicators	Mean					Total		
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD	VI
C. Knowledge, Innovation and Education								
1. Relevant information on disasters is available and accessible at all levels, to all stakeholders.	2.89	3.80	3.60	3.64	2.82	3.35	0.868	MC
2. School curricula, education material, and relevant training include DRRM and recovery concepts and practices.	3.00	3.20	3.60	3.36	2.91	3.22	0.702	MC
3. Research methods and tools for multi-risk assessments and cost-benefit analysis are developed and strengthened.	2.89	3.40	3.80	3.27	2.73	3.22	0.832	MC
4. A Countrywide public awareness strategy exists to stimulate a culture of disaster resilience, with outreach to urban and rural communities.	3.11	3.40	3.90	3.64	2.91	3.39	0.940	MC
Composite Mean						3.29	0.835	MC

Legend:

- 4.20-5.00 – Very Well Capable (VMC)
 - 3.40-4.20 – Very Capable (VC)
 - 2.60-3.40 – Moderately Capable (MC)
 - 1.80-2.60 – Less Capable (LC)
 - 1.00-1.79 – Not Capable (NC)
- D1 – D5 District 1 - 5*

8. Level of the Capabilities of the High-Risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Policies, Plans and Procedures. The data reveals a strong overall capacity with some areas for improvement. With a mean score of 4.30 in M2 (Alabat), classified as "Very Capable (VC)," the indicator "DRRM is an integral objective of environment-related

policies and plans, including for land use, natural resource management, and adaptation to climate change" had the highest mean score. This suggests that DRRM is strongly integrated into environmental policies in Alabat. With a mean score of 2.73 in M5 (Plaridel), the indicator "Economic and productive sectoral policies and plans" had the lowest mean score, falling into the "Moderately Capable (MC)" category. This suggests that Plaridel's procedures for evaluating development project risks are not as strong. The level of capabilities of high-risk schools in disaster response, particularly in terms of policies, plans, and procedures. With a composite mean of 3.46, which is considered "Very Capable (VC)," the data shows that the five municipalities have a generally strong capacity, though there are some noteworthy areas that still need focused improvement. Alabat, the best-performing District, exhibits remarkable integration of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) into more general environmental policies, especially those pertaining to climate change adaptation, land use, and natural resource management.

Table 8 Level of the Capabilities of the High-Risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Policies, Plans and Procedures

Indicators	Mean					Total			
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD	VI	
D. Policies, Plans and Procedures									
1. DRRM is an integral objective of environment-related policies and plans, including land use, natural resource management, and adaptation to climate change	3.22	4.30	4.10	3.45	3.09	3.63	1.038	VC	
2. Social development policies and plans are being coordinated to reduce the vulnerability of populations at risk.	3.33	3.70	3.70	3.45	2.82	3.39	1.002	MC	
3. Economic and productive sectoral policies and plans have been coordinated to reduce the vulnerability of economic activities.	3.11	3.90	4.00	3.73	2.73	3.49	0.946	VC	
4. Planning and management of human settlements incorporate DRRM elements, including enforcement of building codes.	3.44	4.10	4.00	3.18	3.09	3.55	0.966	VC	
5. DRRM measures are incorporated into post-	3.67	3.60	3.70	3.64	3.00	3.51	0.857	VC	

disaster recovery and rehabilitation processes									
6. Procedures are in place to assess disaster risks of major development projects, especially infrastructure.	3.11	3.50	3.70	3.00	2.82	3.22	0.832	MC	
Composite Mean	3.46						0.940	VC	

Legend:

- 4.20-5.00 – Very Well Capable (VMC) D1 – D5 District 1 - 5
- 3.40-4.20 – Very Capable (VC)
- 2.60-3.40 – Moderately Capable (MC)
- 1.80-2.60 – Less Capable (LC)
- 1.00-1.79 – Not Capable (NC)

9. Level of the Capabilities of the High-Risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Capabilities and Mechanism.

The level of capabilities of high-risk schools in disaster response in terms of capacities and mechanisms shows a generally moderate capability, with some areas of strength. A mean score of 4.00 in M3 Calauag, which is classified as "Very Capable (VC)," was the highest for the indicator "Disaster preparedness plans and contingency plans are in place at all administrative levels and regular training drills and rehearsals are held to test and develop disaster response programs." This suggests that Calauag has strong disaster preparedness plans and regularly conducts training drills. The indicator "Financial reserves and contingency mechanisms are in place to support effective response and recovery when required," on the other hand, had the lowest mean score, 2.82 in M5 Plaridel, which put it in the "Moderately Capable (MC)" group. The overall capabilities of high-risk schools in disaster response, particularly in terms of policies, plans, and procedures, show a generally strong capacity across the five municipalities, with a composite mean score of 3.46, categorized as "Very Capable (VC)." While the municipalities demonstrate solid disaster preparedness, certain areas require focused improvement. Alabat stands out as the highest-performing District, exhibiting exceptional integration of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) into broader environmental policies, particularly those related to climate change adaptation, land use, and natural resource management.

Table 9 Level of the Capabilities of the High-Risk Schools in Disaster Response in terms of Capabilities and Mechanism

Indicators	Mean					Total		
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Mean	SD	VI
E. Capacities and Mechanisms								
1. Strong policy, technical and institutional capacities and mechanisms for disaster risk management, with a disaster risk reduction perspective are in place	3.00	4.00	3.80	3.45	2.82	3.41	1.023	VC

2. Disaster preparedness plans and contingency plans are in place at all administrative levels and regular training drills and rehearsals are held to test and develop disaster response programmes	3.00	3.80	4.00	3.36	3.00	3.43	0.922	VC
3. Financial reserves and contingency mechanisms are in place to support effective response and recovery when required	3.33	3.30	3.70	3.36	2.82	3.29	0.756	MC
4. Procedures are in place to exchange relevant information during hazard events and disasters and to undertake post event reviews	3.33	3.40	3.90	3.00	2.82	3.29	0.855	MC
Composite Mean						3.36	0.889	MC

Legend:

4.20-5.00 – Very Well Capable (VMC) D1 – D5 District 1 - 5
3.40-4.20 – Very Capable (VC)
2.60-3.40 – Moderately Capable (MC)
1.80-2.60 – Less Capable (LC)
1.00-1.79 – Not Capable (NC)

10. The relationship on the Level of Coordination of School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinator and the Level of Capabilities in Disaster Response of the Risk Schools. Table 10 shows a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.547$) between the two variables, indicating that as the coordination of the DRRMP improves the capabilities in disaster response of the schools also tend to improve. At the 0.01 level ($p = 0.000$), this connection is statistically significant, indicating that the observed association is not the result of chance. Since it seems to be essential to improving schools' readiness and response skills in disaster scenarios, the data emphasizes the need of efficient coordination in disaster risk reduction initiatives. The significant positive correlation implies that schools with better DRRMP coordination are more likely to have stronger disaster response capabilities. This analysis underscores the value of strengthening DRRMP coordination to improve disaster preparedness and response in schools.

Table 10 A statistical table showing the relationship between the Level of Coordination of School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinator and the Level of Capabilities in Disaster Response of the Risk Schools

Correlations			DRRMP	Capabilities
Spearman's rho	Coordination	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.547**

	p-value	.	.000
	N	51	51
Capabilities	Correlation Coefficient	.547**	1.000
	p-value	.000	.
	N	51	51

**** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of this study, the following findings were derived: Coordinating the School's Disaster Risk Reduction Management in high-risk schools across different disaster management areas shows a generally positive outcome. Disaster prevention and mitigation obtained a composite mean of 3.59 and was categorized as "Moderately Coordinated," indicating that while there is coordination in this area, there is room for further improvement. On the other hand, disaster preparedness obtained a composite mean of 3.69. It was categorized as "Well Coordinated," indicating that while there is coordination in this area, there are minor areas for refinement. Meanwhile, disaster response had a composite mean of 3.69 and was categorized as "Well Coordinated," suggesting that while there is coordination in this area, there are minor areas for refinement. Lastly, disaster recovery and rehabilitation were rated higher, with composite means of 3.59 categorized, interpreted as "Well Coordinated." This indicates that while there is coordination in this area, there are minor areas for refinement. The strong coordination in these aspects supports the broader international consensus, including frameworks such as the UNISDR (2015) and the ASEAN Safe Schools Initiative, which advocate for institutionalizing DRRM practices at the school level. Moreover, the importance of integrating both structural and non-structural interventions into disaster recovery is supported by Sumbillo and Madrigal's (2020) study on schools in Negros Island. They found that recovery efforts are most effective when they combine physical rebuilding with community-based training, active stakeholder participation, and long-term planning.

The level of capabilities of the high-risk schools in disaster response in terms of human resources obtained a composite mean of 3.37 with a verbal description of "Moderately Capable." This indicates that while there was a reasonable level of capability, there is room for enhancement to strengthen overall preparedness. Material facilities obtained a composite mean of 3.39 with a verbal description of "Moderately Capable." This indicates that while there was a reasonable level of capability, there is room for enhancement to strengthen overall preparedness. Knowledge, innovation, and education had a composite mean of 3.29 with a verbal description of "Moderately Capable," indicating that while there was a reasonable level of capability, there is room for enhancement to strengthen overall response and preparedness. The policies, plans, and procedures had a composite mean of 3.46 with a verbal description of "Very Capable," indicating that while there was a reasonable level of capability, there was room for enhancement to strengthen the overall response. Lastly, capacities and mechanisms had a composite mean of 3.36 with a verbal description of "Moderately Capable." This indicates that while there was a reasonable

level of capability, there is room for enhancement to strengthen overall response and preparedness. In support of this, Grant (2012), as cited by Tizon and Comighud (2020), stressed the importance of institutionalizing disaster awareness in schools—not just through infrastructure but also through training, education, and communication strategies. These include organizing seminars and drills, using peer education, and leveraging science curricula to foster a culture of preparedness.

Additionally, these findings align with Dela Cruz and Ormilla's (2022) study, which found that many Philippine schools lack sector-specific, localized risk profiles that could direct focused mitigation and readiness plans. Additionally, DRR-related curricula incorporate competencies that enhance resilience and reduce vulnerabilities. Schools and learners cascade knowledge and skills to other community members, making DRR learning through schools possible (Ntin, 2023).

Furthermore, there is no significant relationship between the level of coordination of the Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program and the risk schools' level of capabilities in disaster response. This aligns closely with the fact that preparedness is about anticipating the needs that will arise in emergencies and building capacities through planning and ongoing cultivation. Better coordinating DRRMPs helps schools identify resources, establish preparedness goals, and reduce the adverse effects of disasters. Furthermore, UNESCO (2010), as cited by Peneciba (2020), highlights the importance of appropriate disaster rehabilitation and recovery in restoring the educational environment, further supporting this study's findings. The observed correlation supports the idea that well-coordinated DRRMPs improve immediate disaster responses and facilitate long-term recovery efforts such as rebuilding infrastructure (Terpstra, 2016).

Lastly, the proposed intervention plan aims to strengthen coordination, enhance preparedness, and improve school disaster management capabilities. By targeting specific areas such as disaster prevention and mitigation, disaster response, preparedness, recovery, and rehabilitation, the plan will provide a structured approach to reduce risks, ensure safety, and promote resilience. The intervention seeks to fill gaps identified through prior assessments, ensuring that schools are not only ready for immediate response but also equipped for long-term recovery and rehabilitation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. In high-risk schools, preparedness, response, and recovery efforts are moderate, and disaster management coordination is generally good. However, there is still an opportunity for improvement, particularly in disaster mitigation and prevention, which could use more bolstering.
2. High-risk schools exhibit moderate capabilities in various areas of disaster response. While they are moderately capable in human resources, material facilities, knowledge, and innovation, their policies, plans, and procedures are a notable strength, categorized

as "Well Capable." This suggests that the schools have a solid foundation but may need to invest further in building capacity in other areas for more comprehensive disaster management.

3. There is a significant relationship between the level of coordination of the Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program and the risk schools' level of capabilities in disaster response.

4. The proposed intervention plan focuses on enhancing coordination and improving school disaster management capabilities. Addressing prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery aims to build resilience and ensure schools are better equipped for immediate and long-term disaster management. The plan addresses identified gaps and further strengthens schools' disaster readiness.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Based on the study's findings, limited training and seminars are conducted about SDRRM so that Department of Education Officials may provide additional resources, training, and monitoring to improve disaster prevention, mitigation, and overall school preparedness.

2. According to the study results, limited programs and projects related to DRRM are implemented so that school heads may integrate disaster risk reduction programs into school operations and promote collaboration to enhance preparedness and resilience.

3. As indicated by the study data, the coordinators moderately coordinated with the DRRM activities. SDRRM Coordinators may focus on improving disaster prevention and mitigation coordination while strengthening partnerships with local and national agencies.

4. Since this study focused on the level of coordination of SDRRM coordinators and the level of capabilities in disaster response for enhancement, future researchers may explore the relationship between disaster risk reduction efforts and factors like community support, infrastructure, and the long-term impact on students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher secured approvals from the appropriate authorities and stakeholders before gathering data. To obtain permission to conduct the study, formal request letters were sent to the superintendent of the Public Schools Division, district supervisors, and school principals. Permission was obtained from the research instrument's original author to guarantee the material's ethical use further. Google Forms was used to administer the survey to internet-connected participants. Printed copies of the study were sent to schools with spotty or limited connectivity to ensure inclusivity and equal participation

opportunities. The voluntary completion and submission of the survey forms implied informed consent.

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REFERENCES

- Dela Cruz, R. D., & Ormilla, R. C. (2022). Disaster risk reduction management implementation in the public elementary schools of the Department of Education, Philippines. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 4(2), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.18485/ijdrm.2022.4.2.1>
- Catanus, R. J. (2018). Disaster risk reduction management in elementary schools. Foundation University, Dumaguete City, Philippines
- Comighud, S. M. (2020). Coordination of the public schools' disaster risk reduction management program and level of capabilities to respond. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 9(4), 752. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340630378>
- Gaillard, J. C., Liamzon, C. C., & Villanueva, J. D. (2012). Natural disaster? A retrospect into the causes of the late 2004 typhoon disaster in Eastern Luzon, Philippines. *Environmental Hazards*, 7(4), 257–270.
- Grant, T. (2012). Bring your first aid: Unannounced drill. *Journal of School Nursing*, 18(3), 174–178.
- National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Framework (NDRRMF). (2011).
- Ntim, N. S. (2023). Mainstreaming disaster risk reduction in the curricular of colleges of education in Ghana. *Open Journal of Educational Research*, 3, Article 627. <https://doi.org/10.31586/ojer.2023.627>
- Peneciba, E. P. (2020). The implementation of disaster risk reduction management program in preparedness and awareness for school safety: Basis for

- intervention plan. *Asian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7(1), 1–xx.
<https://www.multidisciplinaryjournals.com>
- Republic Act 10121, The Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010.
- Sumbillo, L. Z., Jr., & Madrigal, D. V. (n.d.). Disaster risk reduction management practices of Augustinian Recollect schools in Negros Island. *Main Journal*, 3(2).
<https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v3i2.220>
- Terpstra, T. (2017). Public perception of risk. *Risk*, 4, 2–1.
- Tizon, R. T., & Comighud, S. M. T. (2020). Implementation of the Public Schools' Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program and Level of Capabilities to Respond. <https://knowledgecenter.ubt-uni.net/conference/2020/ed/1/>
- UNESCO. (2010). Reaching the marginalized. EFA Global Monitoring Report 2010. Paris: UNESCO. Retrieved from
<http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0018/001866/186606E.pdf>
- United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction. (2015c; 2016). Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030.